

Technical Report: A Systematic Mapping Study of Information Retrieval-Based Requirements Traceability Methods

1.Extracted Data

1.1.Extracted Data for RQ1

Index	Title	Year	Venue	Publication type
S1	An empirical study on recovering requirement-to-code links	2016	ICSE	Conference
S2	An Empirical Study on Source Code Feature Extraction in Preprocessing of IR-Based Requirements Traceability	2022	QRS	Conference
S3	Configuring Latent Semantic Indexing for Requirements Tracing	2015	ICSE	Conference
S4	IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model	2022	QRS	Conference
S5	Analyzing closeness of code dependencies for improving IR-based Traceability Recovery	2017	SANER	Conference
S6	An empirical study on the importance of source code entities for requirements traceability	2014	ESE	Journal
S7	Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery	2021	FITEE	Journal
S8	A Complete Traceability Methodology Between UML Diagrams and Source Code Based on Enriched Use Case Textual Description	2022	IJCAI	Journal
S9	Achieving better requirements to code traceability: which refactoring should be done first?	2016	QUATIC	Conference
S10	Using Consensual Biterms from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	2022	ASE	Conference
S11	A Semantic Approach for Traceability Link Recovery in Aerospace Requirements Management System	2015	ISADS	Conference
S12	An IR-based Artificial Bee Colony Approach for Traceability Link Recovery	2020	ICTAI	Conference
S13	Propagating frugal user feedback through closeness of code dependencies to improve IR-based traceability recovery	2022	ESE	Journal
S14	Leveraging BPMN particularities to improve traceability links recovery among requirements and BPMN models	2022	RE	Journal
S15	Combining VSM and BTM to improve requirements trace links generation	2019	SEKE	Conference
S16	TRIAD: Automated Traceability Recovery based on Biterm-enhanced Deduction of Transitive Links among Artifacts	2024	ICSE	Conference
S17	Visualizing Software Repositories through Requirements Trace Links	2023	RE	Conference
S18	Multi-Objective Information Retrieval-Based NSGA-II Optimization for Requirements Traceability Recovery	2020	EIT	Conference
S19	Filtering of false positives from IR-based traceability links among software artifacts	2017	I2CT	Conference
S20	Quality improvements for trace links between source code and requirements	2016	REFSQ	Conference
S21	Evaluation of Natural Language Processing for Requirements Traceability	2022	SOSE	Conference
S22	ATLaS: A Framework for Traceability Links Recovery Combining Information Retrieval and Semi-supervised Techniques	2019	EDOC	Conference
S23	An Automated Hybrid Approach for Generating Requirements Trace Links	2020	IJSEKE	Journal
S24	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Various IR Models for Requirements Traceability	2021	ICCMST	Conference
S25	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Multi-Objective Approach	2017	CEC	Conference and Workshop Papers
S26	Supporting Requirements to Code Traceability Creation by Code Comments	2021	IJSEKE	Journal
S27	SANAYOJAN A framework for traceability link recovery between use-cases in software requirement specification and regulatory documents	2014	ICSE	Conference
S28	Evolving Software Trace Links between Requirements and Source Code	2018	ICSE	Conference
S29	Interactive recovery of requirements traceability links using user feedback and configuration management logs	2015	CAiSE	Conference
S30	Supporting requirements to code traceability through refactoring	2014	RE	Journal
S31	Recovering traceability links between requirements and source code using the configuration management log	2015	IEICE	Journal
S32	Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for Effective Automated Requirements Traceability	2018	IST	Journal
S33	Using Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	2019	ICPC	Conference
S34	Adaptive User Feedback for IR-Based Traceability Recovery	2015	ICSE	Conference
S35	On the role of semantics in automated requirements tracing	2015	RE	Journal
S36	Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery	2024	RE	Conference
S37	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Fine-Grained Query Expansion Analysis	2023	Information	Journal

S38	DF4RT: Deep Forest for Requirements Traceability Recovery between Use Cases and Source Code	2023	SMC	Conference
S39	Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability	2024	JKSUCIS	Journal
S40	MLTracer: An Approach Based on Multi-Layered Gradient Boosting Decision Trees for Requirements Traceability Recovery	2024	IJCNN	Conference

1.2.Extracted Data for RQ2

Index	Title	IR Model	Stage	Scenarios
S1	An empirical study on recovering requirement-to-code links	VSM	Preprocessing Stage	Generation
S2	An Empirical Study on Source Code Feature Extraction in Preprocessing of IR-Based Requirements Traceability	VSM LSI	Preprocessing Stage	Generation
S3	Configuring Latent Semantic Indexing for Requirements Tracing	LSI	Links Generation Stage	Maintenance
S4	IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model	VSM	Links Generation Stage Links Refinement Stage	Generation
S5	Analyzing closeness of code dependencies for improving IR-based Traceability Recovery	VSM LSI JS	Links Refinement Stage	Generation
S6	An empirical study on the importance of source code entities for requirements traceability	LSI TM(LDA)	Preprocessing Stage	Validation
S7	Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery	VSM	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S8	A Complete Traceability Methodology Between UML Diagrams and Source Code Based on Enriched Use Case Textual Description	LSI	Preprocessing Stage	Generation
S9	Achieving better requirements to code traceability: which refactoring should be done first?	VSM LSI	Preprocessing Stage	Generation
S10	Using Consensual Biterns from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	VSM LSI JS	Links Refinement Stage Preprocessing Stage	Generation
S11	A Semantic Approach for Traceability Link Recovery in Aerospace Requirements Management System	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S12	An IR-based Artificial Bee Colony Approach for Traceability Link Recovery	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S13	Propagating frugal user feedback through closeness of code dependencies to improve IR-based traceability recovery	VSM LSI JS	Links Refinement Stage Preprocessing Stage	Validation
S14	Leveraging BPMN particularities to improve traceability links recovery among requirements and BPMN models	LSI	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S15	Combining VSM and BTM to improve requirements trace links generation	VSM TM(BTM)	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S16	TRIAD: Automated Traceability Recovery based on Bitern-enhanced Deduction of Transitive Links among Artifacts	VSM LSI JS	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S17	Visualizing Software Repositories through Requirements Trace Links	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Application
S18	Multi-Objective Information Retrieval-Based NSGA-II Optimization for Requirements Traceability Recovery	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S19	Filtering of false positives from IR-based traceability links among software artifacts	VSM	Links Refinement Stage	Validation
S20	Quality improvements for trace links between source code and requirements	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S21	Evaluation of Natural Language Processing for Requirements Traceability	VSM	None	Validation
S22	ATLaS: A Framework for Traceability Links Recovery Combining Information Retrieval and Semi-supervised Techniques	VSM LSI TM(LDA)	Links Generation Stage	Validation
S23	An Automated Hybrid Approach for Generating Requirements Trace Links	VSM TM(BTM)	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S24	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Various IR Models for Requirements Traceability	VSM LSI JS	None	Generation
S25	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Multi-Objective Approach	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Maintenance
S26	Supporting Requirements to Code Traceability Creation by Code Comments	VSM	Preprocessing Stage	Maintenance
S27	SANAYOJAN A framework for traceability link recovery between use-cases in software requirement specification and regulatory documents	TM(LDA)	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S28	Evolving Software Trace Links between Requirements and Source Code	VSM LSI	Links Generation Stage	Maintenance
S29	Interactive recovery of requirements traceability links using user feedback and configuration management logs	VSM	Links Generation Stage Links Refinement Stage	Maintenance

S30	Supporting requirements to code traceability through refactoring	VSM LSI	Preprocessing Stage	Maintenance
S31	Recovering traceability links between requirements and source code using the configuration management log	VSM	Preprocessing Stage Links Generation Stage Links Refinement Stage	Maintenance
S32	Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for Effective Automated Requirements Traceability	VSM JS	Links Refinement Stage	Generation
S33	Using Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	VSM LSI JS	Links Refinement Stage	Generation
S34	Adaptive User Feedback for IR-Based Traceability Recovery	VSM	Links Refinement Stage	Validation
S35	On the role of semantics in automated requirements tracing	VSM	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S36	Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S37	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Fine-Grained Query Expansion Analysis	IR-based+	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S38	DF4RT: Deep Forest for Requirements Traceability Recovery between Use Cases and Source Code	VSM LSA LDA JS BM25	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S39	Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability	VSM LSA LDA JS BM25	Links Generation Stage	Generation
S40	MLTracer: An Approach Based on Multi-Layered Gradient Boosting Decision Trees for Requirements Traceability Recovery	VSM LSI LDA BM25	Links Generation Stage	Generation

1.3.Extracted Data for RQ3

Index	Title	Enhancement strategy
S1	An empirical study on recovering requirement-to-code links	Verb-object Phrases
S2	An Empirical Study on Source Code Feature Extraction in Preprocessing of IR-Based Requirements Traceability	Code Feature Extraction, Annotation Importance Assessment, and Annotation Redundancy Removal
S3	Configuring Latent Semantic Indexing for Requirements Tracing	Heuristic Measures
S4	IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model	Code Class Structure
S5	Analyzing closeness of code dependencies for improving IR-based Traceability Recovery	Analyzing Close Relations of Code Dependencies
S6	An empirical study on the importance of source code entities for requirements traceability	Improved Term Weighting Scheme
S7	Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery	Analyzing Close Relations
S8	A Complete Traceability Methodology Between UML Diagrams and Source Code Based on Enriched Use Case Textual Description	Traceability Rules
S9	Achieving better requirements to code traceability: which refactoring should be done first?	Refactoring
S10	Using Consensual Biterms from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Consensual Biterms Global and Local Weight
S11	A Semantic Approach for Traceability Link Recovery in Aerospace Requirements Management System	Integrating semantic similarity
S12	An IR-based Artificial Bee Colony Approach for Traceability Link Recovery	Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) Algorithm
S13	Propagating frugal user feedback through closeness of code dependencies to improve IR-based traceability recovery	Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code Analyzing Closeness of Code Dependencies
S14	Leveraging BPMN particularities to improve traceability links recovery among requirements and BPMN models	BPMN-specific approaches
S15	Combining VSM and BTM to improve requirements trace links generation	Hybrid Method
S16	TRIAD: Automated Traceability Recovery based on Biterm-enhanced Deduction of Transitive Links among Artifacts	Consensual Biterms and Transitive Relationships
S17	Visualizing Software Repositories through Requirements Trace Links	None
S18	Multi-Objective Information Retrieval-Based NSGA-II Optimization for Requirements Traceability Recovery	Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II)
S19	Filtering of false positives from IR-based traceability links among software artifacts	Correlation Among Classes
S20	Quality improvements for trace links between source code and requirements	Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II)

S21	Evaluation of Natural Language Processing for Requirements Traceability	None
S22	ATLaS: A Framework for Traceability Links Recovery Combining Information Retrieval and Semi-supervised Techniques	Semi-Supervised Techniques
S23	An Automated Hybrid Approach for Generating Requirements Trace Links	Hybrid Method Genetic Algorithm
S24	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Various IR Models for Requirements Traceability	None
S25	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Multi-Objective Approach	Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II)
S26	Supporting Requirements to Code Traceability Creation by Code Comments	Code Comments
S27	SANAYOJAN A framework for traceability link recovery between use-cases in software requirement specification and regulatory documents	None
S28	Evolving Software Trace Links between Requirements and Source Code	Trace Link Evolver
S29	Interactive recovery of requirements traceability links using user feedback and configuration management logs	Configuration Management Log User Feedback
S30	Supporting requirements to code traceability through refactoring	Refactoring
S31	Recovering traceability links between requirements and source code using the configuration management log	Configuration Management Log Commonality and Variability Analysis (CVA) Classification
S32	Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for Effective Automated Requirements Traceability	ConPOS approach
S33	Using Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code
S34	Adaptive User Feedback for IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Adaptive User Feedback
S35	On the role of semantics in automated requirements tracing	Semantic Augmentatio
S36	Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery	filtering requirements
S37	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Fine-Grained Query Expansion Analysis	fine-grained correlation analysis and query expansion
S38	DF4RT: Deep Forest for Requirements Traceability Recovery between Use Cases and Source Code	IR Features as Input to ML Models
S39	Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability	IR Features as Input to ML Models
S40	MLTracer: An Approach Based on Multi-Layered Gradient Boosting Decision Trees for Requirements Traceability Recovery	IR Features as Input to ML Models

1.4.Extracted Data for RQ4

Index	Title	Source Artifact	Target Artifact	Datasets
S1	An empirical study on recovering requirement-to-code links	Requirements	Code	eTour iBooks SMS EasyClinic
S2	An Empirical Study on Source Code Feature Extraction in Preprocessing of IR-Based Requirements Traceability	Requirements Use cases Use cases	Code Code Code	iTrust eTOUR Albergate EasyClinic SMOS
S3	Configuring Latent Semantic Indexing for Requirements Tracing	Requirements Defect Reports Use Cases Change Requests	Requirements Use Cases Test Cases Use Cases	MODIS CM-1 EasyClinic MR0 MR1 MR2
S4	IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model	Requirements	Code	iTrust
S5	Analyzing closeness of code dependencies for improving IR-based Traceability Recovery	Requirements	Code	iTrust Gantt jHotDraw
S6	An empirical study on the importance of source code entities for requirements traceability	Requirements	Code	iTrust Lucene Pooka
S7	Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery	Use Case Requirements Requirements Requirements Use Case	Test Case Design Use Case Requirements Code	EasyClinic CMI-NASA Pine GANNT iTrust
S8	A Complete Traceability Methodology Between UML Diagrams and Source Code Based on Enriched Use Case Textual Description	Use Cases	Code	Car rental Customer Relationships system

S9	Achieving better requirements to code traceability: which refactoring should be done first?	Use Cases	Code	iTrust eTour
S10	Using Consensual Biterms from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Requirements	Code	iTrust GanttProject Maven Pig Infinispan Seam2 Drools Derby Groovy
S11	A Semantic Approach for Traceability Link Recovery in Aerospace Requirements Management System	Requirements	Requirements	Borland CaliberRM
S12	An IR-based Artificial Bee Colony Approach for Traceability Link Recovery	Requirements Use Cases	Code	EBT Albergate eTour
S13	Propagating frugal user feedback through closeness of code dependencies to improve IR-based traceability recovery	Requirements	Requirements	iTrust GanttProject Maven Pig8 Infinispan Drools Derby Seam Groovy
S14	Leveraging BPMN particularities to improve traceability links recovery among requirements and BPMN models	BPMN models	Requirements	Industrial case study Academic case study
S15	Combining VSM and BTM to improve requirements trace links generation	Use case Requirements Requirements	Test Case Test Case Requirements	WARC EasyClinic EBT
S16	TRIAD: Automated Traceability Recovery based on Biterm-enhanced Deduction of Transitive Links among Artifacts	Requirements Use cases Requirements	Code Code Requirements	Dronology WARC EasyClinic EBT Libest
S17	Visualizing Software Repositories through Requirements Trace Links	Requirements Requirements Requirements	Issues Requests Commits	public GitHub repository of a group of computer engineering students for their software engineering course
S18	Multi-Objective Information Retrieval-Based NSGA-II Optimization for Requirements Traceability Recovery	Requirements	Code	EBT Albergate eTour
S19	Filtering of false positives from IR-based traceability links among software artifacts	Use Cases	Code	iTrust
S20	Quality improvements for trace links between source code and requirements	Requirements Use Cases	Code Code	Mylyn iTrust
S21	Evaluation of Natural Language Processing for Requirements Traceability	Requirements	Requirements	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)
S22	ATLaS: A Framework for Traceability Links Recovery Combining Information Retrieval and Semi-supervised Techniques	Requirements	Models	Aggreg0 Aggreg1 Aggreg2 Aggreg3
S23	An Automated Hybrid Approach for Generating Requirements Trace Links	Use Case Requirements Requirements Use Cases	Test Case Test Case Requirements Code	WARC subset 1 WARC subset 2 EBT EasyClinic eTour
S24	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Various IR Models for Requirements Traceability	Requirements	Code	Activemq Cassandra Derby Hive Mina Pig Solr Synapse Tika Xerces2j
S25	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Multi-Objective Approach	Requirements	Code	LEDA Albergate ETOUR
S26	Supporting Requirements to Code Traceability Creation by Code Comments	Use Cases	Code	eTour iTrust
S27	SANAYOJAN A framework for traceability link recovery between use-cases in software requirement specification	Use Cases	Regulatory Documents	The experiments on real-world data obtained from software projects of a

	and regulatory documents			large global Information Technology (IT) services company
S28	Evolving Software Trace Links between Requirements and Source Code	Requirements	Code	Dronology
S29	Interactive recovery of requirements traceability links using user feedback and configuration management logs	Requirements	Code	An enterprise system
S30	Supporting requirements to code traceability through refactoring	Requirements	Code	iTrust eTour WDS
S31	Recovering traceability links between requirements and source code using the configuration management log	Requirements	Code	CUnit Network Control System
S32	Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for Effective Automated Requirements Traceability	Requirements	Code	iTrust Lynx Pooka SIP Communicator
S33	Using Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Requirements	Code	iTrust Maven Pig Gantt Infinispan
S34	Adaptive User Feedback for IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Use Cases Test Cases Code UML Requirements	Code Code JSP Code Requirements	Easy-Clinic i-Trust Modis
S35	On the role of semantics in automated requirements tracing	Requirements	Code Design	iTrust eTour CM-1
S36	Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery	Requirements	Code	eTour iTrust SMOS eAnci LibEST
S37	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Fine-Grained Query Expansion Analysis	Requirements	Code	eTour iTrust SMOS eAnci
S38	DF4RT: Deep Forest for Requirements Traceability Recovery between Use Cases and Source Code	Use case	Code	eTour iTrust Pig Easy-Clinic
S39	Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability	Requirements	Code	eTour iTrust SMOS eAnci
S40	MLTracer: An Approach Based on Multi-Layered Gradient Boosting Decision Trees for Requirements Traceability Recovery	Requirements Requirements Use case Use case Use case	Design Requirements Code Test case UML	eTour iTrust CM-1 GANTT Easy-Clinic

1.5.Extracted Data for RQ5, RQ6 and RQ7

Index	Title	Intercept points	Year	Measure
S1	An empirical study on recovering requirement-to-code links	Threshold	2016	Recall Precision F-Measure
S2	An Empirical Study on Source Code Feature Extraction in Preprocessing of IR-Based Requirements Traceability	Threshold	2022	Recall Precision F-Measure
S3	Configuring Latent Semantic Indexing for Requirements Tracing	Not write	2015	MAP AP
S4	IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model	Threshold	2022	Recall Precision F-Measure
S5	Analyzing closeness of code dependencies for improving IR-based Traceability Recovery	Thresholds	2017	Recall Precision F-Measure, MAP AP
S6	An empirical study on the importance of source code entities for requirements traceability	Threshold	2014	Recall Precision F-Measure

S7	Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery	Threshold	2021	Recall Precision MAP AP
S8	A Complete Traceability Methodology Between UML Diagrams and Source Code Based on Enriched Use Case Textual Description	Threshold	2022	Recall Precision
S9	Achieving better requirements to code traceability: which refactoring should be done first?	Threshold	2016	None
S10	Using Consensual Biterms from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Threshold	2022	Precision Recall F- Measure AP MAP
S11	A Semantic Approach for Traceability Link Recovery in Aerospace Requirements Management System	Threshold	2015	Recall Precision
S12	An IR-based Artificial Bee Colony Approach for Traceability Link Recovery	Iteration	2020	Recall Precision F-Measure
S13	Propagating frugal user feedback through closeness of code dependencies to improve IR-based traceability recovery	Threshold	2022	Recall Precision F-Measure AP MAP
S14	Leveraging BPMN particularities to improve traceability links recovery among requirements and BPMN models	Not write	2022	Recall Precision F-Measure MCC AUC
S15	Combining VSM and BTM to improve requirements trace links generation	Threshold	2019	Recall Precision
S16	TRIAD: Automated Traceability Recovery based on Biterm-enhanced Deduction of Transitive Links among Artifacts	Threshold	2024	Recall Precision F-Measure AP MAP
S17	Visualizing Software Repositories through Requirements Trace Links	Threshold	2023	Recall Precision F-Measure
S18	Multi-Objective Information Retrieval-Based NSGA-II Optimization for Requirements Traceability Recovery	Iteration	2020	Recall Precision F-Measure
S19	Filtering of false positives from IR-based traceability links among software artifacts	Iteration	2017	Recall Precision F-Measure
S20	Quality improvements for trace links between source code and requirements	Threshold	2016	Recall Precision
S21	Evaluation of Natural Language Processing for Requirements Traceability	Threshold	2022	Recall Precision F-Measure
S22	ATLaS: A Framework for Traceability Links Recovery Combining Information Retrieval and Semi-supervised Techniques	Threshold	2019	Recall Precision F-Measure
S23	An Automated Hybrid Approach for Generating Requirements Trace Links	Selectivity	2020	Recall Precision F-Measure Selectivity
S24	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Various IR Models for Requirements Traceability	Not write	2021	Recall Precision F-Measure
S25	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Multi-Objective Approach	Iteration	2017	Recall Precision
S26	Supporting Requirements to Code Traceability Creation by Code Comments	Not write	2021	Recall Precision MAP AP
S27	SANAYOJAN A framework for traceability link recovery between use-cases in software requirement specification and regulatory documents	Not write	2014	AP MAP
S28	Evolving Software Trace Links between Requirements and Source Code	Not write	2018	Recall Precision F-Measure
S29	Interactive recovery of requirements traceability links using user feedback and configuration management logs	Threshold	2015	Recall Precision F-Measure

S30	Supporting requirements to code traceability through refactoring	Threshold	2014	Recall Precision MAP DiffAR
S31	Recovering traceability links between requirements and source code using the configuration management log	Threshold	2015	Recall Precision F-Measure
S32	Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for Effective Automated Requirements Traceability	Not write	2018	Recall Precision MAP AP
S33	Using Frugal User Feedback with Closeness Analysis on Code to Improve IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Threshold	2019	Recall Precision F-Measure MAP AP
S34	Adaptive User Feedback for IR-Based Traceability Recovery	Threshold	2015	Recall Precision
S35	On the role of semantics in automated requirements tracing	Threshold	2015	Recall Precision
S36	Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery	Threshold	2024	Recall Precision F-Measure
S37	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Fine-Grained Query Expansion Analysis	Threshold	2024	Recall Precision F-Measure MAP AP
S38	DF4RT: Deep Forest for Requirements Traceability Recovery between Use Cases and Source Code	Threshold	2023	Recall Precision F-Measure
S39	Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability	Not write	2024	Recall Precision F-Measure
S40	MLTracer: An Approach Based on Multi-Layered Gradient Boosting Decision Trees for Requirements Traceability Recovery	Not write	2024	Recall Precision F-Measure

1.6.Extracted Data for RQ8

	Research Method	Context	Subjects	Scale	Technology Transfer Stage
S1	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S2	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S3	Laboratory Experiment	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S4	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S5	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S6	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S7	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S8	Case Study	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S9	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S10	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S11	Laboratory Experiment	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S12	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S13	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S14	Case Study	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S15	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S16	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S17	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S18	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation

S19	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S20	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Toy Example	Academic Validation
S21	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S22	Case study	Industry	Practitioner	Industrial	Dynamic Validation in Industry
S23	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S24	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S25	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S26	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S27	Case study	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S28	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S29	Laboratory Experiment	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S30	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S31	Laboratory Experiment	Industry	Researcher	Industrial	Static Validation in Industry
S32	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S33	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S34	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S35	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S36	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S37	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S38	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S39	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation
S40	Laboratory Experiment	Academia	Researcher	Down-Scaled Real Example	Academic Validation

2. Search process record

Database	Number of searches	Number of repetitions in each database	Number of each database (After deleting repetitions)	Number of repetitions in all 6 databases	Total number (After deleting repetitions)
IEEE Xplore	371	156	215	691	2052
Engineering Village	1826	829	997		
Springer	131	43	88		
Science Direct	219	52	167		
ACM	108	14	94		
Google scholar	1797	615	1182		

2.1. Search records

Search terms:

P1	requirement traceability
P2	requirement trace
P3	requirement tracing
P4	traceability recovery
P5	trace assessment
P6	trace maintenance
I1	information retrieval
I2	IR
I3	semantic

(1) IEEE Xplore

	Command Search
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	323+48
Total	371

The screenshot of search process in IEEE Xplore:

Showing 1-25 of 323 results for (requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement tracing OR traceability recovery OR trace assessment OR trace maintenance) AND (information retrieval OR IR OR semantic) ×

Filters Applied: 2014 - 2023 ×

Conferences (265)
 Journals (54)
 Magazines (3)
 Books (1)

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Year

Range Single Year
 2014 2023

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IRRT: An Automated Software Requirements Traceability Tool based on Information Retrieval Model ⓘ
 Sen Zhang; Hongyan Wan; Yong Xiao; Ziruo Li
 2022 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability, and Security Companion (QRS-C)
 Year: 2022 | Conference Paper | Publisher: IEEE
 Abstract HTML PDF

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Showing 1-25 of 48 results for **((requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement tracing OR traceability recovery OR trace assessment OR trace maintenance) AND (information retrieval OR IR OR semantic))**
 Filters Applied: 2024 x

Conferences (30) Journals (17) Early Access Articles (1)

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Requirements Classification for Traceability Link Recovery

Tobias Hey; Jan Keim; Sophie Corallo

2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)

Year: 2024 | Conference Paper | Publisher: IEEE

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(2) Engineering Village

	Abstract + Title + Keywords (Index term)
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	1604+222
Total	1826

The screenshots of search process in EI

Engineering Village Search [Search history](#) [Alerts](#) [Selected records](#) [More](#) [Create account](#)

Databases Date Sort by Autostemming Search codes Browse indexes

1,604 records found in Compendex for 1884-2024: (((requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement tracing OR traceability recovery OR trace assessment OR trace maintenance) AND (information retrieval OR IR OR semantic)) WN ALL) * + (2023 OR 2022 OR 2021 OR 2020 OR 2019 OR 2018 OR 2017 OR 2016 OR 2015 OR 2014) WN YR * + [english] WN LA *

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All Open Access 401

Gold 78

Hybrid Gold 66

Bronze 105

Green 217

Preprint articles are included in these search results. To exclude them, please filter by document type. [Learn more](#)

Display: 25 results per page

- Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery**
- A Systematic Literature Review of Issue-Based Requirement Traceability (Open Access)**

The screenshot shows the Engineering Village search interface. The search query is "(requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement trac". The results page shows 222 records found in Compendex for 2024-2024. The search criteria are: (((requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement tracing OR traceability recovery OR trace assessment OR trace maintenance) AND (information retrieval OR IR OR semantic) WN ALL) AND (English WN LA)). The results are sorted by Relevance. A refine sidebar is visible on the left with options for physical properties and categories. The first result is titled "Blockchain technology for requirement traceability in systems engineering" by Elapolu, Mohan S.R. et al., published in Information Systems, v 123, July 2024.

(3) Springer

	Abstract + Title + Keywords (Index term)
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	118+13
Total	131

The screenshots of search process in Springer:

The screenshot shows the Springer search interface. The search query is "requirement traceability OR requirement trace OR requirement tracing". The results page shows 118 results. The search criteria are: ("requirement traceability" OR "requirement trace" OR "requirement tracing"). The results are sorted by Relevance. A content type filter is visible on the left with options for Chapter (76), Conference paper (57), Article (42), and Research article (39). The first result is titled "Analyzing close relations between target artifacts for improving IR-based requirement traceability recovery" by Haijuan Wang, Guohua Shen, ... Kai Chen in Frontiers of Information Technology & Electronic Engineering, published on 28 July 2021.

3 We are improving our search experience. To check which content you have full access to, or for advanced search, [go back to the old search.](#)

Search for articles, journals, books, authors, videos

("requirement traceability" OR "requirement trace" OR "requirement tracing")

Showing 1-13 of 13 results 2024-2024 Sort by (updates page) Relevance

Content type Chapter (11) Conference paper (8) Article (2) Research article (2)

Date published Last 3 months

Conference paper Preview access

Improving Requirement Traceability by Leveraging Video Game Simulations in Search-Based Software Engineering

Video games pose different challenges during development and maintenance than classic software. For example, common and widespread assets, that are...

Javier Verón, Raúl Lapeña, ... Francisca Pérez in *Advanced Information Systems Engineering* 2024

Conference paper Preview access

An Automated Ontology-Based Requirements Traceability Technique in Agile Software Development Context

(4) Science Direct

	Abstract + Title + Keywords (Index term)
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	205+14
Total	219

The screenshots of search process in Science Direct

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Find articles with these terms

("requirement traceability" OR "requirement trace" OR "requirement tracing" OR "traceabi")

Year: 2014-2023 Advanced search

205 results sorted by relevance | date

Download selected articles

Research article Full text access

1 **Requirements traceability technologies and technology transfer decision support: A systematic review**
Journal of Systems and Software, December 2018
Bangchao Wang, Rong Peng, ... Zhuo Wang

Research article Full text access

2 **Exploiting Parts-of-Speech for effective automated requirements traceability**
Information and Software Technology, February 2019
Nasir Ali, Haijeng Cai, ... Jameledine Hassine

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2023 (22) 2022 (19) 2021 (17)

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Article type

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Find articles with these terms
 ("requirement traceability" OR "requirement trace" OR "requirement tracing" OR "traceabi...
 Advanced search

14 results sorted by relevance | date

Refine by:

Years

- 2025 (1)
- 2024 (14)
- 2023 (22)
- Show more

Article type

- Review articles (2)
- Research articles (12)

Publication title

- Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences (3)
- Journal of Industrial Information Integration (2)

Research article

Multi-type requirements traceability prediction by code data augmentation and fine-tuning MS-CodeBERT
 Computer Standards & Interfaces, August 2024
 Ali Majidzadeh, Mehrdad Ashtiani, Morteza Zakeri-Nasrabadi

Research article • Open access

An empirical study on the state-of-the-art methods for requirement-to-code traceability link recovery
 Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences, July 2024
 Bangchao Wang, Zhiyuan Zou, ... Xingfu Li
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Research article • Open access

Enhancing requirements-to-code traceability with GA-XWCoDe: Integrating XGBoost, Node2Vec, and genetic algorithms for improving model performance and stability
 FEEDBACK

(5) ACM Digital Library

	Anywhere
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	91+17
Total	108

An example screenshots of search process in ACM Digital Library:

ACM DIGITAL LIBRARY Associated for Computing Machinery

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Search Results ("requirement traceability" OR "requirement trace" OR "requirement t...
 Advanced Search

Applied Filters

2014 - 2023 Clear All

People

Names Institutions Authors

91 Results for: [[All: "requirement traceability" OR [All: "requirement trace" OR [All: "requirement tracing" OR [All: "traceability recovery" OR [All: "trace assessment" OR [All: "trace maintenance"]] AND [All: "information retrieval" OR [All: "ir" OR [All: "semantic"]] AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2014 TO 12/31/2023)]]

Searched The ACM Full-Text Collection (756,065 records) | Expand your search to The ACM Guide to Computing Literature (3,749,657 records)

RESULTS Showing 1 - 20 of 91 Results

Select All per page: 10 20 50 Recency

RESEARCH-ARTICLE Using Consensual Biterms from Text Structures of Requirements and Code to Improve IR-

(6) Google Scholar

	Anywhere
(P1 OR P2 OR P3 OR P4 OR P5 OR P6) AND (I1 OR I2 OR I3)	1640+157
Total	1797

An example screenshots of search process in Google Scholar

2.2. List of excluded studies at the full-text eligibility stage

Index	Title	Exclusion Reason
1	Recovering Traceability Links between Release Notes and Related Software Artifacts	not focus on RT
2	Enhancing the Performance of Ir-Based Traceability Recovery of Requirement Artifacts Using Noun Phrases	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
3	Advancing Trace Recovery Evaluation-Applied Information Retrieval in a Software Engineering Context	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
4	Exploring Semantics of Software Artifacts to Improve Requirements Traceability Recovery: A Hybrid Approach	not focus on IR techniques
5	Towards Recovering Fault Traceability Links by Using Information Retrieval Technique	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
6	Estimating the number of remaining links in traceability recovery	not focus on IR techniques
7	Comparing traceability through information retrieval, commits, interaction logs, and tags	not focus on RT
8	Automating traceability link recovery through classification	not focus on IR techniques
9	Requirements Traceability Through Information Retrieval Using Dynamic Integration of Structural and Co-change Coupling	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
10	Requirements traceability recovery for the purpose of software reuse: an interactive genetic algorithm approach	not focus on IR techniques
11	AVIATE: Exploiting Translation Variants of Artifacts to Improve IR-based Traceability Recovery in Bilingual Software Projects	not focus on RT
12	Traceability in the Wild: Automatically Augmenting Incomplete Trace Links	not focus on RT
13	Enhancing Unsupervised Requirements Traceability with Sequential Semantics	not focus on IR techniques
14	Information retrieval versus deep learning approaches for generating traceability links in bilingual projects	not focus on RT
15	Analyzing Tools and Techniques for Evaluating Requirements Traceability	not empirical study
16	A multi-faceted roadmap of requirements traceability types adoption in SCRUM: An empirical study	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
17	Enhancing Traceability Link Recovery with Unlabeled Data	not focus on IR techniques
18	Traceability Support for Multi-Lingual Software Projects	not focus on RT
19	Modeling Traceability Between Requirements and Coding Using the Property Listing Task	not focus on IR techniques
20	Constructing Traceability Links between Software Requirements and Source Code Based on Neural Networks	not focus on IR techniques
21	Semi-supervised Pre-processing for Learning-Based Traceability Framework on Real-World Software Projects	not focus on RT
22	Automatic traceability link recovery via active learning	not focus on IR techniques
23	MBSE-driven visualization of requirements allocation and traceability	not focus on IR techniques
24	Search-Based Requirements Traceability Recovery	not focus on IR techniques
25	Traceability Link Recovery between Requirements and Models using an Evolutionary Algorithm Guided by a Learning to Rank Algorithm: Train Control and Management Case	not focus on IR techniques
26	Combining Machine Learning and Logical Reasoning to Improve Requirements Traceability Recovery	not focus on IR techniques
27	Enhancing Automated Requirements Traceability by Resolving Polysemy	not focus on IR techniques
28	Recovering Traceability Links Between Code and Specification Through Domain Model Extraction	not focus on IR techniques
29	Evaluation of Textual Similarity Techniques in Code Level Traceability	not focus on RT

30	Requirements Traceability: Recovering and Visualizing Traceability Links Between Requirements and Source Code of Object-oriented Software Systems	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
31	Multilevel Traceability Links Establishments Between SOFL Formal Specifications and Java Codes Using Multi-dimensional Similarity Measures	not focus on RT
32	A Cross-Level Requirement Trace Link Update Model Based on Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers	not focus on IR techniques
33	An Improved Approach based on Balanced Keyword Weight to Traceability Recovery	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
34	Clustering for traceability managing in system specifications	not focus on IR techniques
35	Recovering Trace Links Between Software Documentation And Code	not focus on IR techniques
36	Cross-level Requirement Traceability: A Novel Approach Integrating Bag-of-Words and Word Embedding for Enhanced Similarity Functionality	their venues are not included in the Conference Partner list
37	Recovering Semantic Traceability between Requirements and Source Code Using Feature Representation Techniques	not focus on IR techniques
38	Semantic Recovery of Traceability Links between System Artifact	not focus on IR techniques
39	Do Information Retrieval Algorithms for Automated Traceability Perform Effectively on Issue Tracking System Data?	not focus on RT
40	How Effective Is Automated Trace Link Recovery in Model-Driven Development?	not focus on RT